

POLYARYLENE SULFIDE
HIGH PERFORMANCE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

J. E. O'Connor, T. P. Murtha, A. South
Phillips 66 Company
Advanced Composites Division
Bartlesville, Oklahoma 74004
USA

and

M. R. Lindstrom, A. Y. Lou
Phillips Petroleum Company
Phillips Research Center
Bartlesville, Oklahoma 74004
USA

ABSTRACT

Polyarylene sulfides are a family of highly aromatic polymers characterized by their excellent chemical resistance, thermal stability, good physical strength, inherent flame resistance and easy processibility. This exceptional balance of properties has led to their use as matrix resins for long fiber reinforced composites. Reinforcing fibers such as glass, carbon and aramid have been incorporated into these polyarylene sulfide resins in a variety of forms including random mat, woven fabric and continuous rovings. The resulting prepreg materials have been used to fabricate high performance polyarylene sulfide composite structures by a variety of processes. The composite structures possess good mechanical properties, toughness characteristics and solvent resistance. As the thermal stability of the polymer matrix increases, increased property retention of the composite structures is observed.

INTRODUCTION

Long fiber reinforced polyarylene sulfide (PAS) materials are a recent entry into the field of high performance composites. These polyarylene sulfide composites, as well as several other thermoplastic polymer composites, are presently being evaluated for the several advantages they offer over current thermoset polymer composites. These advantages include improved toughness and damage tolerance characteristics, decreased moisture absorption, improved reparability and the potential for lower manufacturing costs due to faster processing cycles.

Several different fibers (carbon, glass, aramid) as well as different forms of fibers (random mat, woven fabric, continuous rovings) have been used to successfully reinforce specific members of the polyarylene sulfide family. For example, composite materials containing a polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) matrix reinforced with random glass fiber mat,^[1] woven glass or carbon fiber fabric,^[2] and continuous carbon, aramid or glass fiber rovings,^[3] have all been reported. In addition, other polyarylene sulfide polymers reinforced with continuous carbon fiber rovings have also been reported.^[4,5] Thus, a wide range of composite properties and processing characteristics are available for these materials.

A description of the arylene sulfide polymer family as well as the fiber reinforced composite materials are presented in this paper. Processing methods used to fabricate composite structures from these polyarylene sulfide materials are discussed. Properties and test data for these composite structures are also presented.

POLYARYLENE SULFIDE POLYMERS

Arylene sulfide polymers are a class of thermoplastic materials represented by the general formula $(-Ar-S)_x$. The polymers are composed of a high degree of aromatic units which are interconnected with divalent sulfur atoms. This combination of aromatic character and sulfur linkages results in a family of polymers with inherent flame resistance, good thermal stability, superior chemical and solvent resistance, and an excellent balance of physical properties.

The simplest member of the polyarylene sulfide family is polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) which consists of a polymer backbone of alternating disubstituted aromatic rings and divalent sulfur atoms. PPS is an engineering thermoplastic that is semicrystalline in nature with a glass transition temperature (T_g) of 85°C and a crystalline melting point (T_m) of 285°C . Due to its semicrystalline nature, it possesses excellent solvent, chemical and corrosion resistance properties.

The next member of the polyarylene sulfide family, PAS-1, is also semicrystalline in nature and possesses higher thermal transitions. The polymer has a T_g of 145°C and a T_m of 340°C . These higher thermal transitions plus the semicrystalline character of the polymer give it excellent solvent and chemical resistance as well as improved retention of properties at high temperatures.

Another member of the polyarylene sulfide family, PAS-2, is amorphous in nature and has a glass transition temperature of 215°C. PAS-2 shows unusually good chemical resistance for an amorphous polymer and shows little or no decrease in tensile properties after exposure to a wide variety of solvents. The reason for the exceptional solvent resistance of this amorphous polyarylene sulfide is potentially due to a strong association of the PAS-2 molecules leading to a pseudocrystalline character.[5]

The combination of high thermal transitions, excellent chemical resistance, inherent flame resistance, good toughness and physical properties have made members of the polyarylene sulfide family excellent candidates as matrix resins for high performance composites. Nominal properties of the polyarylene sulfide polymers are listed in Table 1.

Table 1
Nominal Properties of Polyarylene Sulfide Polymers

	<u>PPS</u>	<u>PAS-1</u>	<u>PAS-2</u>
Density, g/cc	1.36	1.36	1.40
Tensile Strength, psi	12,100	13,600	14,500
Elongation, %	2.5	4.0	8.0
Flexural Strength, psi	23,800	23,400	25,700
Flexural Modulus, psi	590,000	565,000	460,000
Izod Impact, ft lb/in			
Notched	0.4	0.5	0.8
Unnotched	7.6	12.0	25.2
Oxygen Index, %	44	-	46
Tg, °C	85	145	215
Tm, °C	285	340	-

POLYARYLENE SULFIDE COMPOSITES

PPS Random Mat Composites

Polyphenylene sulfide has been combined with either chopped or continuous mat fiber reinforcements. Fiber contents typically range from 10 to 40% and are dependent on the fiber type (glass, carbon), fiber form (chopped mat, continuous swirl mat) and intended application. The mat reinforced PPS materials possess extremely good toughness and are used in applications where a combination of high strength, chemical resistance and toughness are desired.

The mat reinforced PPS materials are processed by a method referred to as stamp molding. This process is a rapid compression molding technique in which precut sheets of random fiber reinforced PPS are heated to 315-345°C and quickly transferred to a positive pressure mold in a fast closing press. Application of 1500-6000 psi pressure forces the PPS polymer matrix and mat reinforcement to flow together to fill the mold. Upon cooling and solidification, the part can be removed from the mold. Typical cycle times for parts up to 0.25" thick, range from 30-90 seconds. Since fiber length is maintained, high strength high impact parts are produced. Nominal properties of various fiber mat reinforced PPS stamp molded sheets are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2
Properties of Random Mat PPS Composites

	Glass <u>Swirl Mat</u>	Glass <u>Chop Mat</u>	Carbon <u>Chop Mat</u>
Fiber Content, wt%	40	30	30
Density, g/cc	1.66	1.59	1.40
Tensile Strength, ksi	23.4	18.0	29.4
Tensile Modulus, msi	2.0	-	-
Elongation, %	2.0	1.5	-
Flexural Strength, ksi	36.7	27.0	34.6
Flexural Modulus, msi	1.5	1.0	2.0
Compression Strength, ksi	38.0	35.0	-
Izod Impact, ft lb/in			
Notched	14.0	7.0	2.4
Unnotched	25.0	18.0	7.0

PPS Woven Fabric Composites

Polyphenylene sulfide has been reinforced with glass fiber or carbon fiber woven fabric reinforcement to make a fabric prepreg product. Plies of the woven fabric prepreg are consolidated with heat and pressure to form a laminate. The laminates can be fabricated in a heated press, vacuum bag or autoclave. Since the matrix resin is thermoplastic, no cure or crosslinking cycle is required and the molding time is short. Nominal properties for press molded (316°C; 100 psi; 5 minute dwell time) woven fabric reinforced PPS composite laminates are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Properties of Woven Fabric (Satin Weave) PPS Composites

	<u>Glass</u>	<u>Glass</u>	<u>Carbon</u>
Fiber Content, wt%	40	60	60
Density, g/cc	1.6	1.8	1.6
Tensile Strength, ksi	24.0	36.0	100.0
Tensile Modulus, msi	2.2	3.5	11.2
Elongation, %	1.3	1.3	0.9
Flexural Strength, ksi	30.0	53.0	108.0
Flexural Modulus, msi	1.8	3.0	7.2
Compression Strength, ksi	32.0	43.0	58.0

Woven fabric reinforced PPS laminates are ideally suited for a subsequent thermoforming process in which fiber orientation is maintained in the finished part.^[2] In this process the laminated PPS composite sheet is heated to approximately 316°C and quickly transferred to a mold and formed into a final shape using moderate pressure (15-50 psi). Either matched mold thermoforming or vacuum forming is possible. Large parts which do not possess detailed and complicated design can be fabricated by this process. Parts with curved surfaces such as skins, covers, panels and trays are easily thermoformed. The low pressure forming requirements permit the use of inexpensive tools made from wood or soft metals. Cycle times are fast and thermoformed parts can be fabricated in 1-10 minutes depending on the heating time required (which depends on laminate thickness and oven configuration).

PAS Continuous Fiber Composites

Continuous, unidirectional fiber rovings have been used to reinforce several members of the polyarylene sulfide family. The impregnation process produces either unidirectional prepreg tape or tow with good fiber wetting and dispersion. Continuous polyphenylene sulfide prepreg tapes containing glass, aramid or carbon fibers have been made. In addition, PAS-1 and PAS-2 continuous prepreg tapes containing carbon fibers have been fabricated.

Since the polyarylene sulfides are thermoplastic polymers, the prepreg has no shelf life restrictions and no special storage conditions are required. Although the prepreg exhibits no tack, several plies can be held in place by spot melting them together. Equipment to seam prepreg tapes together to make wider plies has been demonstrated for fabrication of large laminates. Hot head thermoplastic tape

laying equipment is also currently being developed for automated construction of thermoplastic laminates.

Composite laminates containing fiber reinforced polyarylene sulfide are readily fabricated from the prepreg using standard layup procedures. Laminates can be molded quickly because the molding does not involve a chemical crosslinking or curing process. The molding cycle consists only of melting, application of consolidation pressure, and cooling. Typical molding conditions for the polyarylene sulfide composites are 316°C and 150 psi for PPS; 371°C and 150 psi for PAS-1; 330°C and 300 psi for PAS-2. Nominal properties of glass, aramid and carbon fiber reinforced polyphenylene sulfide are listed in Table 4 and nominal properties of carbon fiber reinforced PPS, PAS-1 and PAS-2 are compared in Table 5.

TABLE 4

Properties of Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced PPS Composites

	<u>E Glass</u>	<u>Aramid</u> 49	<u>Carbon</u> AS4	<u>Carbon</u> AS4	<u>Carbon</u> IM6
Fiber Content, vol%	57.0	53.3	53.4	60.5	51.1
Void Content, vol%	1.0	1.2	0.5	0.5	1.1
Density, g/cc	2.03	1.38	1.58	1.61	1.55
Tensile Strength, ksi	121	160	230	265	298
Tensile Modulus, msi	7.6	9.3	17.5	19.4	20.3
Elongation, %	1.7	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.3
Flexural Strength, ksi	166	86	250	275	210
Flexural Modulus, msi	6.1	6.9	15.8	17.0	19.1
Compression Strength, ksi	116	28	125	136	114
Short Beam Shear, ksi	6.2	4.6	10.5	10.0	6.1
Interlaminar Fracture Toughness(G_{1c}), in-lb/in ²	7.2	4.2	4.7	4.8	5.8

As expected, elevated temperature testing of the PAS composites shows that as the thermal transitions of the polymer matrix increase, better property retention at high temperatures is observed. Thus, at 350°F, carbon fiber PAS-2 composites retain 80-90% of their strength and 100% of their modulus. However, due to the semicrystalline regions of PPS and PAS-1 polymer composites, good elevated temperature properties are observed despite the lower glass transition temperatures. Figures 1 and 2 show tensile and flexural property retention of carbon fiber reinforced polyarylene sulfide composites.

Figure 1. TENSILE PROPERTY RETENTION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER POLYARYLENE SULFIDE LAMINATES

Figure 2. FLEXURAL PROPERTY RETENTION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER POLYARYLENE SULFIDE LAMINATES

In addition to fabricating laminates from unidirectional PAS prepreg tape, the continuous fiber prepreg materials have been used to fabricate braided, woven, filament wound and pultruded type structures. Well consolidated, low void structural shapes and profiles have been produced. Due to their thermoplastic nature, the application of heat and pressure to these structural shapes permits additional shaping or postforming of these structures. Localized heating permits bending, compressing, flaring or other reshaping of the structure to alter its shape if required. The successful fabrication of these polyarylene sulfide composite structures by such processing methods will certainly extend the use of these materials into new composite products.

TABLE 5

Properties of Unidirectional Carbon Fiber Reinforced PAS Composites

	<u>PPS</u>	<u>PAS-1</u>	<u>PAS-2</u>
Fiber Content, vol%	60.5	59.1	53
Void Content, vol%	0.5	0.2	0.3
Density, g/cc	1.61	1.60	1.60
Tensile Strength, ksi	265	227	215
Tensile Modulus, msi	19.4	17.9	19.0
Elongation, %	1.2	1.1	1.1
Flexural Strength, ksi	275	198	241
Flexural Modulus, msi	17.0	16.1	16.0
Compression Strength, ksi	136	-	130
Short Beam Shear, ksi	10.0	13.0	11.3
Interlaminar Fracture Toughness(G_{1c}), in-lb/in ²	4.8	5.0	-

CONCLUSIONS

A family of thermoplastic composite materials and products based on polyarylene sulfide polymers as the composite matrix have been developed. The arylene sulfide polymers are characterized by their excellent corrosion resistance, inherent flame resistance, thermal stability, toughness and good physical properties. Different types of fiber such as glass, aramid and carbon as well as a variety of fiber forms such as mat, woven fabric and continuous roving have been impregnated with members of the polyarylene sulfide family. Prepreg types include stampable sheet, fabric prepreg and unidirectional tape or tow.

Composite structures have been produced from the prepreg materials by processes including stamp molding, laminating (press, vacuum bag, autoclave), thermoforming, automated tape laying, braiding, weaving, pultruding and filament winding. The successful fabrication of polyarylene sulfide composite structures by such a wide variety of methods indicates the versatility of these composite materials.

Good ambient temperature properties of all the polyarylene sulfide composites are observed. As the thermal transitions of the polymer matrix increase, so does the elevated property retention of the composite structure. PPS and PAS-1 composites show good thermal stability and excellent chemical resistance due to the semicrystalline nature of the polymer matrix. PAS-2 composites show excellent thermal stability due to the high T_g of the polymer and unusually good chemical resistance for an amorphous polymer.

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